

Effect of Money Supply in the Private Sector with Francophone CFA and Currency Devaluation

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ABSTRACT

This study aims at assessing the effect of money supply in the private sector with francophone CFA and currency devaluation. Monetary policy can be defined as the process by which the government, central bank, or monetary authority of a country or group of countries control the supply of money, availability of money, and cost of money or rate of interest to attain a set of objectives oriented towards the growth and stability of the economy. Fourteen countries of the Franc zone over the period of 2012- 2024 using a dynamic panel model was considered to examine the impact on Francophone CFA and currency devaluation. The analysis reveals that money supply has significant positive effect on economic growth, while total reserves and inflation have a negative effect. However the negative effect of domestic credit provided by banking sector can be reversed through allocation of funds to those projects for which the social returns are the highest through allocation of funds to local industries. The results show significant positive impact on money supply in private sector with Francophone CFA for the periods. The study recommends the need for government to improve on the macroeconomic environment through the harmonization of monetary and fiscal policies in order to ensure stability of the economic aggregates. Also, attention should be focused on deepening the financial sector in Francophone through the creation of modern, efficient and strong financial institution that will mobilize the idle financial resources domiciled outside the financial institution. Furthermore, government should have sound, credible and feasible policies to strengthen financial system. The policies should be given priority to develop financial sector.

Key Words: Money, Supply, Private, Sector, Francophone, CFA, Currency, Devaluation

INTRODUCTION

The Franc zone is an economic, monetary and cultural area that is equivalent to none other in the world. It is made up of very diverse states and territories and results from developments and changes in the former French colonial empire (bank of France report 2010). After attaining their independence, most of the newly-created African states decided to remain within a homogenous group characterized by a new institutional framework and a common exchange rate mechanism. The franc zone is made up of France and 15 African states: Benin, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Guinea Bissau, Mali, Niger, Senegal and Togo in West Africa, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, Equatorial Guinea and Gabon in Central Africa, and the Comoros. The

Franc zone is made up of two monetary unions: the West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU) and the Central African Economic and Monetary Community (CEMAC). The treaty instituting the Central African Economic and Monetary Community was signed on 16 March 1994 (by the presidents of Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, Equatorial Guinea and Gabon), resulting in the creation of two entities: an economic union and a monetary union. The Treaty on West African Economic and Monetary Union was signed by the Heads of State of Benin, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Mali, Niger, Senegal and Togo meeting in Dakar on 10 January 1994. This treaty has four main strands.

The central bank of West African states (BCEAO) is an international public institution with head office in Dakar (Senegal). It defines and implements monetary policies in WAEMU, ensures the banking system's stability, implements WAEMU's exchange rate policies under the terms set out by the council and manages the official exchange reserves of member countries. The Bank of Central African states (BEAC) with head office in Yaoundé (Cameroon) has the tasks of defining and setting the union's monetary and the official reserves of the member countries. Also to promote the smooth operation of payment and settlement systems. The primary objective of BEAC is to ensure the monetary stability.

The 14 African countries in the franc zone account for nearly one third of all sub-Saharan African states. Yet in terms of population and output the zone is far smaller. However, during a June 2007 meeting in N'djamena (Chad), member heads of state agreed to institutional reforms in CEMAC to strengthen regional policy making. Overview to only 17% of the population of Sub Saharan Africa and is in fact less than the population of Africa's most populous country, Nigeria. The franc zone accounts for about 15% of Africa's GDP and produces 22% of its oil. The economic landscape of the franc zone is heterogeneous not only between the two unions but even within each grouping. The production structures and structural indicators for WAEMU and CEMAC differ significantly. Though WAEMU has more than doubled the population of CEMAC, its average per capital income in 2006 was less than half the CEMAC level. Measured by the share of exports to crop, WAEMU is also less open. The monetary policy of CEMAC is affected by the economic performance of the region. The monetary authority of BEAC decided to devaluate CFA franc in 1994 in order enhance economic activity.

In 2001 the aim of monetary policy of BEAC was price stability and the promotion of save economic growth in countries (BEAC report 2001), based on this, the monetary supply increased by 13.7% compared to 2000 and the credit to the economy increased by 12% in Cameroon. In Central African Republic, the money supply decreased by 1.1% and the credit to the economy increased by 9.2%, the net debt on state also increased by 38.3% due to difficulties of public.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

The CFA franc zone consists of 14 countries in sub-Saharan Africa, each affiliated with one of two monetary unions. Benin, Burkina Faso, Côte D'Ivoire, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, Niger, Senegal, and Togo comprise the West African Economic and Monetary Union, or WAEMU, founded in 1994 to build on the foundation of the West African Monetary Union, founded in 1973. The

remaining six countries — Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Republic of Congo, Equatorial Guinea, and Gabon — comprise the Central African Economic and Monetary Union, or CAEMC. These two unions maintain the same currency, the CFA franc, which stands for Communauté Financière Africaine (African Financial Community) within WAEMU and Coopération Financière en Afrique Centrale (Financial Cooperation in Central Africa) within CAEMC. WAEMU and CAEMC account for 14 percent of Africa's population and 12 percent of its gross domestic product (GDP).

All of these countries except Guinea-Bissau and Equatorial Guinea were colonies of France and maintain French as an official language. Guinea-Bissau was ruled by Portugal, and today its official language is Portuguese, while Equatorial Guinea was ruled by Spain, and today both Spanish and French are its official languages. The three countries featured in the video vary widely in geography, culture, and history. Côte D'Ivoire and Cameroon, for example, have tropical coastlines with beautiful, palm-lined beaches and dense, verdant forests. Mali, which is largely desert, is home to the storied trading city of Tombouctou (Timbuktu) and occupies territory that was once part of the great empires of Mali, Ghana, and Songhai. Although French is the official language in all three countries, each boasts linguistic diversity. Nearly 80 percent of Mali's population, for example, communicates in Bambara, while many Cameroonians speak English as a first language (part of the country was once under British rule), or one of 24 African languages.

CFA Franc Zone Countries Devalue their Currency

Goods produced by the CFA franc zone countries were priced out of the world market when the exchange rate for the CFA franc was artificially high. Partly as a result, these countries' economies grew little or not at all during the 1980s and early 1990s. To address this situation, they consulted with one another and with the IMF and France, after which they made the bold decision to devalue the CFA franc by 50 percent. This meant that as of January 1994, 100 CFA francs equaled 1 French franc, instead of the previous ratio of 50 CFA francs to 1 French franc. Devaluation was aimed to put these countries back on a path of sustainable growth by helping them regain their competitiveness in the world market.

It encouraged exports at the expense of imports because it enabled CFA franc zone countries to sell their products for half as much but required them to buy products from other countries for twice as much. Devaluation was not intended to be a silver bullet, nor did it turn out to be. One of its immediate side effects is a one-time surge in prices, which can lead to inflation. If this occurs, individual purchasing power declines, making it difficult for ordinary citizens to make ends meet. That is why the IMF encourages governments to couple devaluation with sound macroeconomic and structural adjustment policies. The former includes prudent fiscal and monetary policies and an appropriate exchange rate regime. The latter includes trade liberalization, elimination of price controls, diversification of agriculture, reduction of government workforces, spending, and privatization of state-owned industries. These policies often must be implemented simultaneously or in a carefully planned sequence, and thus necessitate a very high level of cooperative decision-making.

Reform Affected Economic Activity in the CFA Franc Zone Countries

The economies of the CFA franc zone countries have grown 5 percent annually since reforms were implemented. The agricultural sector where the majority of the people in Côte D'Ivoire, Cameroon, and Mali are employed has greatly expanded. Also, more people are now purchasing locally produced vegetables, livestock, and other products. Since these countries' products have become more competitive in world markets, they have increased their exports and improved trade balances, in the process revitalizing such industries as logging and textile manufacturing. Trade within the CFA franc zone has also increased. After an initial surge, inflation has been brought under control, which among other things is helping the poor and making these countries more attractive for investment.

Role of IMF Play in the Economic Recovery of the CFA Franc Zone Countries

Prior to devaluation, the IMF outlined what it believed were the policy steps needed to make it work. Later, it provided technical advice to the CFA franc zone countries on how to supervise and regulate banks, how to implement tariff and tax reforms, and how to rein in government spending. The IMF worked to ensure that substantial funds were allocated to health and education and that social safety nets were in place in these countries. It also provided loans, helped to mobilize co-financing from bilateral and multilateral institutions, orchestrated debt relief and debt cancellation by a number of countries, and worked closely with the World Bank to help each CFA franc zone country design an individual adjustment program. IMF loans are intended to temporarily relieve balance of payments problems and support economic reforms. Credits to poor countries are under a special IMF long-term program, the Enhanced Structural Adjustment Facility (ESAF), which provides financing at very low interest rates. This loan program was enhanced and replaced by the Poverty Reduction and Growth Facility in late 1999.

CFA Franc Zone Faces Several Challenges Today

In spite of these encouraging results, much remains to be done if the economies of the CFA franc zone countries are to continue to grow enough to reduce poverty and increase the living standards of their people. In all of these countries, the role of the government needs to be rethought so that it focuses on providing essential public services instead of being directly involved in production, which the private sector often can do more efficiently. These countries also must allocate more money for infrastructure improvement (e.g., roads, bridges, schools, and utilities) and human resources programs (e.g., health care, education, and job training). In addition, private enterprise in CFA franc zone countries must be expanded, a move that requires governments to convince entrepreneurs that new economic policies will be upheld. Each country also must promote good governance by tackling corruption and inefficiency and making its civil service and judicial systems more open and accountable. Finally, all CFA franc zone countries must continue to work together to forge strong and mutually beneficial economic ties. Their regional integration is a stepping-stone to their full integration into the global economy.

Theoretical Framework

Monetarist theory is linked with the significant contributions to monetary policy and theory by the Nobel Prize, winning economists Friedman and Schwartz (1963) based on their work entitled 'A Monetary History of the United States, from 1867 to 1960'. The monetarist postulation is expressed in the Quantity Theory of Money (QTM) represented by the following equation. $MV=PY$. Where, M, V, P, and Y are the supply of money, the velocity of money, the price level, and total output respectively. Based on the assumptions of full employment equilibrium in the long run, a constant velocity of money, and an exogenously determined money supply, the theory holds that an increase in the money supply will temporarily affect output and employment in the short run. However, with the attainment of full employment equilibrium output; further increase in the money supply only serves to increase the price level and not the levels of output and employment. From the postulations of the monetarist school, it can be deduced that monetary policies can be used as short-term stabilization tools to steer economies to full employment equilibrium-output levels when there is disequilibrium. Again, price stability can be achieved if money supply and output grow in tandem through rule-based monetary policy which ensures steady growth in money supply are in line with the expected level of economic activity

Empirical Review

Kumar & Paramani. (2024) examined the effect of monetary policy on manufacturing value added (performance) of the CFA franc zone of SSA based on panel data covering 7 countries in the region from 1995 to 2021. The study employed the panel ARDL model, which is estimated with three dynamic panel estimators, namely Mean Group (MG), Pooled Mean Group (PMG), and Dynamic Fixed Effect to capture the long and short-run response of the manufacturing sector to monetary policy. Lending interest rate, exchange rate, and domestic credits to the private sector were used to capture the monetary policy while manufacturing value added was used as a proxy for manufacturing performance. The control variables included in the model are labour, capital, and trade openness. Findings from the study show that in the short-run, all monetary variables comprising of lending interest rate, credit to the private sector, and exchange rate have no real impact on manufacturing sector performance. However, interest rate and credit to the private sector have significant negative and positive effects on manufacturing performance in the long run. As uncovered in the short run, the exchange rate had no real impact on manufacturing performance in the long run

Opoku Ibrahim, & (2024), inquired into how the CFA franc zone's output and prices were impacted by monetary factors such as the money supply and bank credit. The long-run and short-run impacts, respectively, were estimated using the framework of Vector Error Correction Models (VECMs) and Granger causality models. The researcher documents that money supply and bank credit positively and significantly influence output in the short run but not in the long run. Concerning the policy implication, the observed neutrality of money in the long term suggests that monetary policy can be effectively deployed in the zone as a short-term stabilization tool. Concerning the effect of monetary variables on prices, the empirical evidence made known that monetary policy only mattered in the long run. From the empirical literature review, it is obvious that there are divergent viewpoints on how monetary policy impacts the manufacturing sector.

One noticeable gap in the literature is that very few studies investigate the effect of monetary policy on the manufacturing performance of the CFA franc zone at an extensive cross country level. Despite the exceptional longevity of the CFA franc zone monetary union, and the potential influence its exchange rate targeting monetary policy framework could have on the real sector performance, there are still very few studies that specifically examine the nexus between monetary policy and the manufacturing sector performance in the zone. To address this palpable dearth of empirical evidence and fill this noticeable gap, this study addresses the pertinent research question of ‘what is the impact of monetary policy on the manufacturing performance of the CFA franc zone?’ What impact do key monetary variables such as lending rate, credit availability and exchange rate have on manufacturing performance in the zone? The study tests the null hypothesis that monetary policy does not have any significant effect on the manufacturing performance of the CFA franc zone. (Md Q, & Wei 2018).

The CFA franc zone has some interesting peculiarities due to its long-standing, strong, integrated monetary system concerning its common currency, common monetary policy, and fixed exchange rate regime with the Euro (initially with the French franc). The zone is of particular interest because of the likelihood that its salient monetary features will have some far-reaching implications for the industrial performance and economic growth of the zone (see Amin, 2022; Perez, 2022; Wilson, 2020; Vaillant and Fanti, 2020; Hounsou, 2017). The CFA franc zone, which is dominated by former French colonies in Africa, was formally established by the decree of the French government in 1945. Even though it has existed for such a long time, its skeptics criticize the absence of monetary sovereignty. France has a de facto veto on the central bank board of the CFA franc zone (Samba-Sylla, 2017).

Due to the fixed exchange rate between the CFA franc and the euro, the franc zone countries' monetary and exchange rate policies are also under the control of the European Central Bank, whose monetary orthodoxy includes a bias against inflation that is thought to be detrimental to growth (Obeng-Odoom, 2022; Amin, 2022; Biankola, and Nzaou-Kongo, 2020; Samba-Sylla, 2017). This perspective argues that the CFA franc zone's integrated monetary system, which neither fosters trade integration between member countries nor enhances bank credit to those economies, inhibits industrialization and structural change. For instance, while the average credit-to-GDP ratio for the CFA franc zone is 10.7%, it is around 25% for the non-CFA zone, which includes nations like Nigeria, Ghana, Kenya, Mauritius, and South Africa, and it is around 19% for SSA (World Bank, 2021).

Although monetary policies are critical tools often employed globally by the monetary authorities for regulating the economy, not much is known about their impact on the manufacturing sector of SSA at an extensive cross-country level.

Most of the studies are conducted for developed nations or emerging economies or at best, at the country-specific level (See Liu, et al, 2022; Bellocchi, et al, 2021; Sheikh, et al 2021; Murgia, 2019; Irandoust, 2019; Kilinc and Tunc, 2019; This study is motivated by a dearth of empirical evidence on how monetary policy affects the manufacturing sector performance in the CFA franc zone. This study becomes even more imperative given the theoretical links between the monetary and goods sector, the persistent state of underdevelopment of the manufacturing sector in the

region, and the peculiarities of the zone as a monetary union that has persisted for several decades.

The study contributes to the literature by filling this noticeable gap. Specifically, the contributions are threefold. First, the study provides empirical evidence on the nature and strength of the relationship between monetary policy and the performance of the manufacturing sector in the CFA franc zone, an area where empirical evidence is lacking. Second, its findings lend credence to theoretical postulations on the nexus between monetary policy and the goods sector. Third, based on empirical foundations, the study makes policy suggestions to enhance the development of manufacturing in the zone. The study covers 7 CFA franc zone countries under a dynamic panel framework. The countries included in the study are Cote d'Ivoire, Senegal, Cameroon, Central Africa Republic, Congo, Gabon, and Niger. The countries and the time series for the study have been selected due to data availability. (Begum, & Aziz, 2023).

The studies of Gillman and Kejak (2005), and Fountas et al. (2022) found a negative effect on growth. Trade many authors like Grossman and Helpman (1991), Youth (1995), show the importance of commercial openness. They concluded their work by saying that trade can enhance economic growth. Here it is in percentage of GDP. Lag of GDP annual growth rate. This variable permits us to test the convergence hypothesis. Neoclassical growth models postulate that, a country's per capita growth rate tends to be inversely related to its starting level of income per person. In particular, if countries are similar with respect to structural parameters for preferences and technology, then poor countries tend to grow faster than rich countries (Barro, 1992). Thus, there is a force that promotes convergence in levels of per capita product, so we expect a negative sign. 4.3- Estimation technique. The estimation of dynamic panels shows the problem of autocorrelation of individual specific effect and independent variables, but also the problem of endogeneity of some explanatory variables.

Kilinc, Seven & Yetkiner (2017), empirically investigate the relationship between domestic credit and economic growth in Nigeria, using annual time series data from 1970 to 2012. Some studies have been carried out in developing countries to assess the effect of monetary policy on economic activity. In order to do this, the study employs KPSS unit root test, Vector Autoregressive (VAR) modeling, impulse response function, variance decomposition and granger causality. Firstly, the findings reveal that there is a bi-directional causality and positive relationship between domestic credit and the economic growth in Nigeria. That is, domestic credit does not only contribute positively to economic growth in Nigeria, but the impact is strong and statistically significant. The findings have a strong implication on monetary policy in Nigeria. The major implication is that an efficient financial system is one of the foundations for building sustained economic growth. Considering regulations, institutional constraints and other macro-economic factors militating against domestic credit in the economy, government should make the environment conducive and supportive so that performance is enhanced and good lending behavior guaranteed.

Khan, Siddique & Sarwar, (2023) investigated on the empirical study on the effect of deposit money banks' credits on Nigeria's private sector's investments. The study was evaluated empirically over a period of forty-one years, from 1981 to 2021. Deposit money banks' credits is proxies by bank credits, with interest rate and money supply moderating regressors while private

sector investments is measured as private investments. Utilized for analysis are sourced secondary data from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and the applied methods of analysis include descriptive statistic technique, Augmented Dickey-Fuller's Unit Root test, Auto regressive Distributed Lag technique. The findings obtained showed clearly that private investments and banks' credits were stable at levels, as cost of credit (interest rate) and money (liquidity) supply were stationary at first difference.

In addition, banks' credits had direct and significant effects on the regress and (private investments) in Nigeria, cost of credit had negative but significant bearing on private investments while money supply had positive and significant effects the independent variable. Lastly, there exists long-run equilibrium rapport among private investment, banks' credits, interest (credit) rate and money supply at 5 percent critical level. Sequel to these findings, it is therefore concluded that deposit money banks' credits had significant-positive effects on private sector investments in Nigeria in both short run and long run. It is thus, recommended among others that deposit money banks need encouragement to expand credit extensions to private sector operators for sustainable enhancement of investments in this sector of the economy.

Ohiomu & Oligbi, (2020) examined the effect of money supply on private sector funding in Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to examine the extent to which monetary policy affect private sector funding in Nigeria. Time series data was sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin from 1985-2018. Credit to private sector, credit to core private sector and credit to small and medium scale enterprises sector was used as dependent variables while narrow money supply, broad money supply, large money supply, private sector demand deposit was used as independent variables. Ordinary Least Square (OLS), Augmented Dickey Fuller Test, Johansen Co-integration test, normalized co-integrating equations, parsimonious vector error correction model and pair-wise causality tests were used to conduct the investigations and analysis. The empirical findings revealed that money supply explains 82.1 percent variation on credit to core private sector, 85.2 percent and 23.4 percent of the variation in credit to private sector and credit to small and medium scale enterprises sector. The study conclude that money supply has significant relationship with credit to private sector, credit to core private sector and credit to small and medium scale enterprises sector. From the findings, the study recommends that Central Bank of Nigeria should induce the variations of the amount of money changes through the nominal interest rates. That the monetary authorities should ensure adequate quantity of money supply that positively affect private sector funding in Nigeria.

Olaniyi (2023) carried out a study to reexamine the immediate cause of the alarming rate of inflation in Nigeria which is adversely affecting the general welfare of Nigerian populace. The aim of the study was to empirically investigate the influence of money supply on inflation in Nigeria. Design and methodology approach was employed to co-integrate test and error correction approach on annual time series. Data spanning from 1970 to 2016 was used to ascertain both the long run and short run dynamics relationship among the variables under consideration. The results showed that money supply does not considerably influence inflation both in the long and short run possibly because the country is in recession. The error correction model has the correct sign of negative and it is significant meaning that about 21% of the errors

are corrected yearly. The Granger causality outcome demonstrates that, there is no causality between money supply and inflation in Nigeria within the study period and vice-versa. (Khan, Sherazi, & Liaqat, 2020).

Ohiomu & Oligbi, (2022), aims at providing quantitative analysis of the dynamics of money supply, exchange rate and inflation in Nigeria. The paper utilizes secondary data that were obtained from the International Financial Statistics (IFS), of all variables investigated in the model. The sample covers quarterly data from 1986 to 2008. The model was estimated using Vector Error Correction Mechanism (VECM). The empirical results confirms that in the long run, money supply and exchange rate have significant inverse effects on inflationary pressure, while real output growth and foreign price changes have direct effects on inflationary pressure. The possible justification for the inverse effect of money supply on price level is that inflation may not be due to aggregate demand pressure but rather due to hiccups in the supply chain of goods both from the domestic and foreign supply outlets. Empirical deductions also signify the presence of significant feedback from the long run to short run disequilibrium. However, there exists a causal linkage between inflation, money supply and exchange rate in Nigeria. (Begum, & Aziz, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

This study examined the effect of money supply in the private sector with Francophone CFA and *currency devaluation*. It discovered the relationship between Money supply and Private Sector Credit on economic growth. The data collected for this study was analyzed. The data have been subjected to stationarity test by checking the properties of the data using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, and the Phillips-Perron test. Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was also used to examine the long run and short run relationship among the variables. Furthermore, the Granger causality test was used to determine the direction of causality between the variable. Finally, various diagnostic tests were conducted. The justification behind adopting Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is because after conducting unit root test using augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF) and Philip-Perron (PP) test we found out there is mixture of integration among the variables, some are integrate of order one I(1) while some are integrate of order zero I(0). The data series order of integration does not impose any restriction on its application. The model can be applied regardless of whether variables are I (0) or I (1). In addition, it does not matter whether explanatory variables are exogenous (Pesaran & Shin, 1997). More so, it can be applied to a small sample size study. Thirdly, it estimates the short- and the long-run components of the model simultaneously, removing problems associated with omitted variables and autocorrelation.

Model Specification

The empirical specification of the model to determine the relationship between Money supply, and *private sector with francophone CFA and currency devaluation*, this study adopted the model with modification from the works of Olushola and Uzoma, (2023) However, the choice of variables is based on the consideration of the economic condition of the country. The model is given as: $RGDP = F(M2, PSC, INTR)$ i putting the above equation into an econometric model $RGDP = +\mu$ii

Where: RGDP= Real Gross Domestic Product M2 =Broad Money supply PCS=Private Sector Credit INTR= Real Interest rate: Interest rate was used as control variable. This was introduced aimed at given robust result. Including interest rate as control variable in the model will improve the robustness of the model because it serves as a vehicle for financial intermediation in the economy. It influences saving and investment decision of economic agents. It is used as an instrument in macroeconomic policy. = Parameters μ = Stochastic or error term A priori expectation: $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_3 < 0$. Specification of Autoregressive Distributed Lag (Bound Testing) Model for testing the nexus between private sector with Francophone CFA and currency devaluation.

From the Mundell-Fleming model, interest rates and exchange rates are the monetary variables that determine the equilibrium output. This study's estimation model is geared towards the modification of the theoretical conclusion of the Mundell-Fleming model. Hence credit to the private sector is included as another money variable, in addition to other variables such as labour, capital and trade openness which act as control variables in the model. Therefore, this study has adopted and modified Saibu and Nwosa (2023) and Fasanya (2022) to permit the inclusion of credit to the private sector and other control variables. The mathematical function is expressed as: $Q = f(W, Z)$
(1) Where: Q = private sector with Francophone CFA and currency devaluation W = Vector of monetary policy variables Z = Vector of control variables Based on the above function, Q is the manufacturing sector performance measured by manufacturing value added. W represents the lending interest rate, exchange rate and credit to the private sector, while Z represents labour, capital and trade openness. Therefore, equation (1) becomes: $mva = f(int, exr, cps, lab, cap, top)$ (2) From (2), the empirical model can be specified.

The short run estimates show that all monetary variables of interest rate, exchange rate and credits to the private sector have no real impact with Francophone CFA and currency devaluation even at the 10% level of significance which implies that monetary policy is more in the long run. Meanwhile, the speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium is -0.2735, implying that any disequilibrium that occurs due to shocks will be corrected at a speed of 27.35% annually. A low inflation rate is indispensable to ensure the credibility of monetary policy. This will be captured by the inflation, consumption price (annual growth) in order to take into account the final objective of which is internal and external stability of money.

The overall performance of the countries in the two monetary unions suggests that belonging to the franc zone was definitely beneficial in limiting inflation. In addition, the average growth rate for these countries during 1980-92 was close to that of the other sub-Saharan African countries. These results reflect primarily the relatively restrained monetary policies the unions pursued, the stability of the exchange rate, and the openness of the economies. The CFA zone countries are almost the only ones in Africa that have a virtually fully convertible currency. As a result, internal disequilibria have not resulted in shortages of foreign exchange; the private sector has had access to foreign exchange, and imports have not been constrained by the lack of foreign currency.

The estimated result show significant positive relationship broad money supply and real gross domestic product in the short run at 5% level. Its estimated coefficient being 0.3254. This means that a one percent increase in M2 will yield a 32.54% increase in real GDP. More so, ratio of private sector credit to GDP on the other hand is also estimated have significant positive relationship with real GDP with an estimated co-efficient of 0.2428. This implies that a one percent rise in ratio of private sector credit to GDP will lead to 24.28 percent increase in real GDP which is also significant at 1% level.

CONCLUSION

It is therefore concluded that each country must promote good governance by tackling corruption and inefficiency and making its civil service and judicial systems more open and accountable. Finally, all CFA Franc zone countries must continue to work together to forge strong and mutually beneficial economic ties. Their regional integration is a stepping-stone to their full integration into the global economy. Among others that deposit money banks need encouragement to expand credit extensions to private sector operators for sustainable enhancement of investments in this sector of the economy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of these findings, the study recommends the need for government to improve on the macroeconomic environment through the harmonization of monetary and fiscal policies in order to ensure stability of the economic aggregates. Also, attention should be focused on deepening the financial sector in Francophone through the creation of modern, efficient and strong financial institution that will mobilize the idle financial resources domiciled outside the financial institution. Furthermore, government should have sound, credible and feasible policies to strengthen financial system. The policies should be given priority to develop financial sector. An effective flow of finance to private sector economy is capable to stir prospective investors to invest and raise the nation's productivity; this can be achieved by good monetary policy instrument mix. Lastly, in other to sustain the momentum of growth occasioned by financial development, attention should also be given to the complimentary and coordinated development. The financial system serves as one of the most important synergists to economic development, the system seeks and attract idle funds and savings and allocate same to entrepreneurs, governments, household for investment projects and other purpose with view of returns, this form the basis of the financial development.

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